

Multi-Fidelity Optimization of Turbulence in a Gas Turbine Combustor Simulator

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Combustor turbulence in a gas turbine engine greatly influences the efficiency of the downstream high pressure turbine stage. Here we use a multi-fidelity computational optimization methodology to modify the geometry of a non-reacting combustor simulator such that turbulence properties are optimized at the combustor-turbine interface. We modify the size, orientation, and positioning of the primary and dilution jets to minimize turbulence intensity at the combustor exit while demonstrating negligible or favorable changes to the pressure loss and mixing characteristics of the combustor. The optimization is performed using a machine learning surrogate-assisted genetic algorithm coupled with large eddy simulations (LES) and Reynolds-averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) simulations. High fidelity LES validated against experimental data provides a reference for the RANS simulations and is also used to confirm the improved characteristics of the optimized design. The optimization is performed in three phases: (i) development of a continuously-learning artificial neural network surrogate model, (ii) stochastic optimization with RANS simulations to narrow the parameter space, and (iii) stochastic optimization with a coarse-grid LES to identify the optimal solution. Using this approach, we are able to achieve a 5.35% reduction in turbulence intensity and a 0.42% reduction in pressure loss while maintaining good mixing uniformity at the combustor exit. These changes were enabled primarily by changing the aspect ratio and diameter of the primary zone and dilution jets, as well as the chute height and spacing of the primary zone jets. This successful demonstration of multi-fidelity optimization in the combustor simulator can be extended in the future to the challenge of designing improved gas turbine combustors.

Keywords: Combustor turbine interaction, Turbulence, Large eddy simulation

1 Introduction

Traditionally in gas turbine engine development, the combustor and high pressure turbine stages have not been designed based on considerations of the turbulent flow at the combustor-turbine interface. However, intense free-stream turbulence at the combustor exit, which is generated by the use of impinging jets in crossflow to mix fuel and air, can negatively impact the performance of the downstream turbine. Recent measurements have shown that the turbine loss coefficient is 50% higher in the presence of intense turbulence, resulting in an approximately 1.3% decrease in stage efficiency [1]. As a result, novel combustor designs that reduce exit turbulence while maintaining engine performance are needed to improve overall efficiency.

To address this challenge, here we use multi-fidelity optimization to modify the design of a combustor such that turbulence levels are minimized at the combustor-turbine interface while maintaining low pressure drop across the combustor and desired levels of mixing uniformity. The optimization method is based on a genetic algorithm and uses a combination of physics-based simulations and surrogate models to explore the design space. We demonstrate the potential benefits of the method by controlling the size, orientation, and position of impinging jets in a non-reacting, non-proprietary combustor simulator developed by Folk [1]. Folk [1] used this simulator to experimentally investigate how combustor turbulence affects the total loss in a turbine cascade, finding that exit turbulence reduces the boundary layer shape factor and creates a corresponding increase in turbulent kinetic energy production due to mean shear. These effects were shown to cause a 22% rise in the dissipation coefficient, a 37% rise in profile loss, and a 38% rise in endwall loss. When applied to an engine-representative

high pressure turbine stage, these loss mechanisms caused a 1.3% reduction in first stage efficiency. In the present study, we show that this efficiency can be improved by modifying the geometry of the combustor simulator to reduce turbulence intensity at the combustor exit.

The need for computational optimization is motivated by the difficulty in understanding the dependence of exit turbulence on combustor design parameters. Hot wire measurements cannot be performed due to the high temperatures within the combustor, necessitating the use of more complex techniques such as laser doppler velocimetry (LDV) and laser doppler anemometry (LDA). Zimmerman *et al.* [2] conducted one of the first measurements of combustor turbulence on an Allison Model 250 turboshaft engine using LDV. This study showed that the average turbulence intensity at the combustor exit was between 6% and 10% and was unaffected by the addition of fuel. Subsequently, Bicen *et al.* [3] measured the turbulence in a reacting combustor simulator designed to replicate a Rolls-Royce Gem 60 turboshaft engine. They used LDA to measure turbulence properties for both reacting and non-reacting flows at the combustor exit, finding turbulence intensities as high as 20%. Similar to Zimmerman [2], they found the turbulence intensity to be unaffected by the addition of fuel. This latter finding is important in justifying the present focus on the non-reacting combustor simulator, since it indicates that combustor turbulence can be studied using isothermal non-reacting jets in crossflow.

The computational optimization of combustors to produce low turbulence levels at the combustor exit is a novel concept, primarily because of the many challenges presented by the optimization of turbulent flows [4,5]. These challenges include the unsteady chaotic nature of turbulence, the computational cost of physics-based simulations to test candidate designs, and the complex non-linear dependence of turbulence properties on design parameters. Regarding the first of these challenges, the extreme sensitivity to

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February 1, 2024

Fig. 1 Schematic (left) and computational model (right) of the combustor simulator from Folk [1].

small perturbations can make turbulent applications difficult to optimize when considering local instantaneous flow characteristics [6]. However, turbulence statistics, such as mean velocities and variances, are, in principle, predictable and can be used to formulate objective functions that have well-defined and reproducible dependencies on the parameters of a given problem. In the present study, we construct an objective function based on the turbulence intensity computed from the standard deviation and mean of the velocity.

Regarding the second challenge noted above, previous optimization studies demonstrated the utility of surrogate models in controlling computational cost [7–9]. For example, Toal *et al.* [10] used surrogate models in an optimization approach focused on reducing NO_x emissions, soot, and pressure loss in a combustor. In surrogate modeling, various problem parameters (e.g., flow conditions and geometric parameters) are explored using a higher-fidelity physics-based simulation and an analytical expression is developed that represents the objective function behavior. It is this analytical expression that is then used in the optimization. The forerunner solutions are selected and assessed using the full simulation, the expression is updated, and the process is repeated. Toal *et al.* [10] used multi-fidelity surrogate modeling in which the surrogate function was developed using data from differing levels of simulation mesh density. It was shown that this approach yielded similar or greater reductions in NO_x as compared to using a single higher fidelity approach. In the present study, we also use surrogate models coupled with higher fidelity physics-based simulations to perform the optimization.

Finally, the third challenge noted above regarding the complexity of the design space motivates the use of global population-based optimization methods that allow a more extensive exploration of design parameters and the avoidance of multiple local optima [11,12]. Although such methods are generally computationally expensive, the cost savings enabled by surrogate models make it feasible to use global optimization methods, such as genetic algorithms, with minimal penalty. For example, Ahuja *et al.* [13] used a genetic algorithm to optimize the height, ramp angle, and sweep angle of a swept ramp combustor design in a scramjet engine. Their algorithm had a total of 10 generations, with each generation having 20 members. The best performing member provided a 43% improvement in mixing efficiency over the starting geometry. Based in part on the success of this study, we also use a genetic algorithm in the present work.

This paper is organized into three sections. In the first section, we describe and validate large eddy simulations (LES) and Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) simulations of the combustor simulator. In the second section, we perform a sensitivity analysis using RANS simulations and surrogate modeling to identify the most important geometric parameters in determining turbulence characteristics at the combustor exit. Finally, we outline and

demonstrate a multi-fidelity optimization framework that combines physics-based simulations with a continuously learning surrogate model and a genetic algorithm to optimize turbulence characteristics at the combustor exit. The resulting design is a combustor tuned to the characteristics of an optimal combustor-turbine interface.

2 Numerical Simulations

2.1 Computational geometry and operating conditions.

The combustor simulator we model and optimize here is the same as that developed by Folk [1] to experimentally investigate turbine losses resulting from realistic combustor turbulence. We use experimental data from Folk [1] to validate the LES and RANS simulations used in the optimization. The design of the combustor simulator is shown in Fig. 1.

In the simulations, the combustor simulator domain is $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m} \times 0.75 \text{ m}$ and is symmetric about the x -axis (the axial direction normal to the combustor exit plane). A third of the flow enters through the back plate of the combustor, representing the fuel injectors and wall jets. The remainder of the flow is evenly routed through the two rows of crossflow jets representing the primary zone and dilution jets. The method of turbulence production via jets in crossflow is the same in both the simulator and a real rich-burn, quick-mix, lean-burn (RQL) gas turbine combustor, with the primary difference being the absence of combustion in the present case. However, the measurements of Zimmerman [2], Bicen *et al.* [3], and Moss & Oldefield [14] have shown that turbulence is not dominantly affected by the combustion process and can therefore be adequately represented by isothermal jets in crossflow. There remain numerous other differences between this simulator and a real combustor, such as the absence of swirl, liner film cooling, and turbine endwall cooling. However, the intent of our study is to focus on the characteristics of combustor turbulence at the exit alone, and the optimization framework developed here can be readily extended to other more complicated cases in the future.

The primary cooling and dilution jets have oval, plunged shapes based upon Rolls-Royce design experience to improve jet penetration [15]. The chutes fitted to the jets are thin-walled to minimize flow blockage, with a wall thickness of 2 mm. The jets have a hydraulic diameter of 48 mm and a streamwise-to-transverse aspect ratio of 2.03. The geometric proportions of the jet diameter relative to the turbine axial chord are equivalent to those of engine representative hardware, as suggested by open literature findings from the Oxford combustor turbine interaction rig (based on Rolls-Royce designs) and the Virginia Polytechnic Institute (based on Pratt and Whitney designs) [16,17]. In agreement with these findings, the present work uses a jet diameter to axial chord ratio of 0.21. The integral length scale of the turbulence generated by jets in crossflow has been shown to be on the order of the jet diameter

[16,18]. Therefore, the characteristic spatial scale of the turbulence in the present work is also representative of engine hardware.

The entirety of the combustor simulator shown in Fig. 1 was included in the computational domain. We further extended the computational domain by 0.525 m in the x direction to align with the experimental measurement plane. In the experiment, the flow upstream of the combustor was straightened by several layers of screens. For this reason, the turbulence intensity at the inlet in the simulations was estimated to be less than 0.5%. An inlet velocity of 9 m/s was prescribed in the x direction, resulting in an average outlet velocity of 27 m/s.

2.2 Large eddy simulations (LES). We performed a fine-grid LES for validation against the experimental results of Folk [1] and used the same LES approach on a coarse grid during the optimization described in Section 4. All simulations were performed in OpenFOAM version 2012 [19] using `pimpleFoam`, a pressure-based incompressible solver based on the PIMPLE algorithm, which combines PISO and SIMPLE algorithms. We solved the filtered continuity and momentum equations given by

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial t} + \tilde{u}_j \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x_i} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j}, \quad (2)$$

where \tilde{u}_i and \tilde{p} are the filtered velocity and pressure, respectively, ρ is the density, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and $\tau_{ij} = \tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_j - \tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_j$ is the sub-grid scale (SGS) stress tensor. The filtering operation is implicit when derivatives in Eqs. (1) and (2) are evaluated on a discrete grid, resulting in low-pass filtering at a scale equivalent to the grid size. The SGS stress tensor τ_{ij} was modeled using the one-equation eddy viscosity model [20,21]. We also included a filtered passive scalar $\tilde{\psi}$ in the LES to assess the mixing properties of the combustor. We solved the filtered scalar transport equation given by

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}}{\partial t} + \tilde{u}_j \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}}{\partial x_j} = D \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\psi}}{\partial x_j \partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \sigma_i}{\partial x_i} + S_\psi, \quad (3)$$

where D is the scalar diffusivity, which we set to 1.5×10^{-7} kg/m-s to match the expected diffusivity of gaseous jet fuel [22], $\sigma_i = \tilde{u}_i \tilde{\psi} - \tilde{u}_i \tilde{\psi}$ is the SGS scalar flux, and S_ψ is a scalar source or sink. We represent σ_i using a gradient transport model with a turbulent mass diffusivity equal to the eddy viscosity, corresponding to a turbulent Schmidt number of unity.

We used a cell-centered finite volume method to solve the governing equations. Time stepping was achieved through an implicit Euler scheme. The use of central differencing methods on collocated grids results in decoupling of the velocity and the pressure cell values and leads to pressure oscillations. These oscillations were mitigated using the Rhie-Chow momentum interpolation method [23]. Gauss' theorem was used to evaluate cell gradients with a linear interpolation scheme. A second order upwind-biased linear scheme was used for the spatial discretization of velocity divergence terms and all other divergence terms. To satisfy continuity, we solved the Poisson equation for pressure obtained by applying the divergence to Eq. (2). The resulting pressure distribution was then used for velocity and mass flux corrections at cell faces, a process that was iterated until convergence was reached.

All boundaries of the combustor were modeled as no-slip walls, with the exception of the inlet and the outlet. At the inlet we prescribed a uniform velocity of 9 m/s in the x direction and modeled the outlet as a zero-gradient boundary. The static pressure at the outlet was constrained to be zero and the pressure at the inlet was modeled using a zero-gradient boundary. The explicit scalar source, S_ψ , was set to a value of 1 at the back plate slots of the combustor, with 1 representing purely fuel and 0 representing purely air.

For the fine-grid LES, the nominal unstructured grid size was $3.5 \text{ mm} \times 3.7 \text{ mm} \times 3.4 \text{ mm}$ within the combustor and $0.82 \text{ mm} \times 0.93 \text{ mm} \times 0.84 \text{ mm}$ at the jet surface; the grid in total consisted of 18,268,908 cells. The average $y^+ = u_\tau y / \nu$ value along the jet surface and contraction was 50, where u_τ is the friction velocity and y is the coordinate in the direction normal to the jet surface. We therefore used the `kqRWallFunction`, `nutkWallFunction`, and `epsilonWallFunction` wall models provided by OpenFOAM version 2012 [19] to account for the viscous and buffer regions of the boundary layer. The same overall approach and wall models were also used in the coarse-grid LES, where the nominal grid size was $5.7 \text{ mm} \times 5.9 \text{ mm} \times 5.7 \text{ mm}$, with the smallest grid size of $2.2 \text{ mm} \times 2.4 \text{ mm} \times 2.2 \text{ mm}$ occurring on the jet surface, totalling 1,480,493 cells.

2.3 LES validation. Figure 2 compares the experimentally measured [1] turbulence intensity and axial (i.e., x -direction) velocity profiles at the combustor exit to the same fields generated by the LES. The turbulence intensity is defined as

$$I = \frac{\langle \tilde{u}'_x \tilde{u}'_x \rangle^{1/2}}{\langle \tilde{u}_x \rangle}, \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{u}'_i = \tilde{u}_i - \langle \tilde{u}_i \rangle$ is the fluctuating component of the resolved velocity and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes a time average. Here, we temporally average all quantities over 72 flow-through times. As shown in Eq. (4), to match the single-component hot wire used in the experiment (Dantec 55P11), only the x -component of the velocity is used to compute the turbulence intensity in the LES.

Figure 2 shows that the magnitudes and spatial distributions of turbulence intensity and exit velocity are generally similar between the experiments and fine grid LES. The experimental velocity field, normalized by the average exit plane velocity, is relatively uniform over the exit plane, with a spatial standard deviation of 4.9%. The fine grid LES results also demonstrate good uniformity, with a standard deviation of 3.6%.

Flow angles were also computed in the experiments and we reproduce these measurements in the simulations by calculating the spatially-resolved angle θ from time-averaged resolved velocities as

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\langle \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle \times \hat{\mathbf{i}}}{\langle \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \rangle \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}}} \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{i}}$ is the unit vector aligned with the x -axis. Table 1 shows the resulting spatially averaged and maximum values of θ over the combustor exit plane. These angles are in good agreement between the fine-grid LES and experiments. The total pressure field, and thus the velocity, is the driving force in the development of secondary flows and heat transfer present in the turbine vane passages. The spatial variations in pressure and temperature at the turbine inlet can result in nonuniform heat transfer to the vanes and blades that can damage these components. Therefore, uniformity of the exit flow field will be another important aspect to demonstrate in the optimized design.

Analysis of the turbulence intensity field shows that some of the upstream flow structures of the jets are retained within the exit flow when evaluated with LES. By contrast, the experimental results show no trace of the upstream flow structures and present as more uniform. The comparison of the standard deviations in turbulence intensity for the experimental and fine grid LES results are 0.67% and 1.16%, respectively. When analyzing the spatial resolution of the hot wire probe used to conduct the experiment (Dantec 55P11), we find that the resolution is nearly three times smaller than that of the LES fine grid where implicit filtering is performed (1.25 mm and 3.6 mm, respectively).

This difference is also evident when evaluating the energy spectra of the two flows in Fig. 3. The larger grid scale used for the LES explains the small discrepancy in the integral time scales listed in Table 1, with the LES being slightly longer. Here, the integral

Fig. 2 Temporally averaged turbulence intensity (top) and normalized exit velocity (bottom) at the combustor exit from experiments [1] (left), fine-grid LES (center) and coarse-grid LES (right).

Table 1 Flow properties $x = 0.525$ m downstream from the combustor exit.

Property	Exp. [1]	Fine LES	Coarse LES
Average TI	17.41%	17.55%	16.60%
Mixing uniformity	-	0.186	0.154
Pressure loss	-	3.97%	5.79%
Max norm. velocity	1.11	1.10	1.07
Integral time (ms)	1.1	1.5	1.9
Integral length (mm)	40.6	50.9	68.0
Mean flow angle	6.56°	4.72°	10.79°
Max flow angle	10.32°	13.81°	34.53°

time scales have been calculated directly from the autocorrelation (Fig. 4), and the integral length scales inferred using the mean axial velocity. As the rate of eddy turnover in the LES is slower, fine scale structures will not dissipate as quickly and this is likely the reason that some upstream structures are retained in these results. Comparing the average turbulence intensities at the exit though, the results are very closely aligned, with the experiment and fine grid LES having average turbulence intensities of 17.41% and 17.55%, respectively. The integral length scales are shown to be on the order of the jet hydraulic diameter. This is consistent with other findings reported in literature [16,18], which state that the integral length scale should be on the order of the feature from which it was generated.

Finally, during the optimization procedure we make use of a coarse grid LES. The coarse grid LES implements the same boundary conditions, schemes, and solvers as the fine grid LES, with the only difference being the grid size of the mesh and the time over which the data is temporally averaged (4.2 flow-through times). Table 1 shows that there is good agreement between the coarse grid and high fidelity LES in the turbulence intensity and mixing uniformity metric, defined as

$$M = \left\langle \frac{\sigma_{\psi}}{\bar{\psi}} \right\rangle, \quad (6)$$

where σ_{ψ} is the standard deviation of $\tilde{\psi}$ over the exit plane. Here and in the following, $\overline{(\cdot)}$ denotes a spatial average over the sampling plane. However, there are substantial differences in the pressure loss. We believe this can be attributed to the coarseness of the mesh in the coarse grid LES, which does not fully resolve curvature on the boundaries and introduces artificial roughness of the surface.

Fig. 3 Energy spectra of the flow for the fine grid LES and experiment with respect to frequency taken at the exit of the combustor, where η is the Kolmogorov scale.

2.4 Reynolds averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) simulations.

In combination with surrogate modeling and coarse grid LES, we also used RANS simulations throughout the optimization and sensitivity analysis in this study. We used the simpleFoam solver in OpenFOAM [19] to model steady-state incompressible turbulent flow in the combustor simulator, with a small modification to include passive scalar transport. The solver applies the SIMPLE algorithm initially proposed by Patankar & Spalding [24]. In the simulations we solve the RANS equations for steady, incompressible flow given by

$$\frac{\partial \langle u_i \rangle}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\langle u_j \rangle \frac{\partial \langle u_i \rangle}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \langle p \rangle}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\nu \left(\frac{\partial \langle u_i \rangle}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \langle u_j \rangle}{\partial x_i} \right) - \langle u_i' u_j' \rangle \right], \quad (8)$$

where we have decomposed the velocity and pressure into mean and fluctuating components as $u_i = \langle u_i \rangle + u_i'$ and $p = \langle p \rangle + p'$. We closed the RANS equations by using the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence

Fig. 4 Normalized autocorrelation used to determine integral time scales from the experimental and fine grid LES results.

model [25] to represent the Reynolds stress tensor $\langle u'_i u'_j \rangle$, where the deviatoric part of the tensor is proportional to the mean strain rate tensor. The $k-\omega$ SST model was chosen because the turbulent eddy viscosity in the model better captures near-wall physics in a wall-bounded flow [6]. We also solved the transport equation for a passive scalar in the RANS simulations. The steady-state scalar transport equation is given as

$$\langle u_j \rangle \frac{\partial \langle \psi \rangle}{\partial x_j} = D \frac{\partial^2 \langle \psi \rangle}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \langle u'_j \psi' \rangle + S_\psi, \quad (9)$$

where the passive scalar is decomposed into a mean and fluctuating component as $\psi \equiv \langle \psi \rangle + \psi'$, and the scalar diffusivity, D , is the same as in Section 2.2.

The governing equations were solved using the same diffusive and gradient schemes as in the LES. We used a second order bounded upwind-biased linear scheme for the discretization of velocity divergence terms. Discretization of divergence terms in all other governing equations used a limiting linear scheme that limits towards upwind in regions of high gradient.

Flow oscillations within the combustor due to the characteristic jet diameter and velocity result in a solution that cannot converge to steady-state if the full combustor is used as the computational domain. Therefore, we only included the top half of the combustor within the domain and forced a symmetric solution through a symmetry boundary on the bottom plane (Fig. 5). The inlet boundary conditions for k and ω were determined based on an inlet turbulence intensity of 0.5% and an inlet turbulence length scale of 32 mm. The remainder of the boundaries were modeled as in the LES. The extension of the domain to the experimental measurement plane was not included for the RANS model. The smallest grid size was 2.1 mm \times 2.3 mm \times 2.1 mm and located at the jet surface. The nominal grid size within the combustor was 4.3 mm \times 4.5 mm \times 4.3 mm, for a total of 1,547,990 cells.

2.5 Comparison of RANS simulations and LES. In RANS modeling, ensemble averaging prevents insight into the smaller-scale transient features of the flow. However, the computational time is drastically improved. A comparison of key optimization objectives and constraints between the RANS, coarse grid LES, and fine grid LES are shown in Table 2.

With RANS, we use the turbulent kinetic energy, k , to define

Fig. 5 Mesh and computational domain for the RANS model.

Table 2 Flow properties at the combustor exit.

Property	RANS	Coarse LES	Fine LES
Average TI	18.5%	28.3%	22.3%
Mixing uniformity	0.923	0.472	0.267
Pressure loss	2.63%	5.79%	3.97%
Model run time (min)	28	67	9,240

the turbulence intensity as

$$I_{\text{RANS}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}k}}{\langle u_x \rangle}. \quad (10)$$

Here, k is determined according to the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model and the axial component of the velocity is used to compute $\langle u_x \rangle$. The mixing uniformity metric is calculated according to

$$M_{\text{RANS}} = \frac{\sigma_{\langle \psi \rangle}}{\langle \psi \rangle}, \quad (11)$$

where $\sigma_{\langle \psi \rangle}$ and $\langle \psi \rangle$ are the spatial standard deviation and mean of the scalar over the exit plane. These expressions are different by necessity than those used for the LES in Eqs. (4) and (6), since only time-averaged quantities are provided by the solution of the RANS equations.

At first glance, we see that there are substantial differences between the RANS and fine grid LES models. We find that a main contributor to this discrepancy is the periodic oscillations observed in the LES, unable to be resolved by RANS and similar to that reported by Tomac et al. [26], that enhances the mixing and turbulent behavior. This oscillation is defined by the movement and bifurcation of the primary zone jets and the interaction of four vortices, which periodically change in shape and size. At a phase angle of 0°, as seen in Fig. 6, all four vortices are equal in size and are located on the four corners of the primary jet impingement plane. The bottom left vortex then grows as it entrains flow from the bifurcating of the upper primary jet, adding momentum to the lower primary jet. This is seen clearly at a phase angle of 45°, where the white arrow indicates movement of the vortex. The upper left vortex begins to expand, fed by the upper primary jet shear layer. With the upper primary jet no longer adding momentum to the lower primary jet, the lower left vortex collapses (seen at a phase angle of 90°). Addition to the lower left vortex from the lower primary jet shear layer then brings these vortices back to equilibrium. This movement indicates one half cycle of the oscillations occurring within the combustor. We find that these oscillations greatly enhance mixing in the combustor and add to the turbulence production; factors that are completely unaccounted for in the RANS model. These oscillations are driven by the flow rate and size of the

Fig. 6 Velocity streamlines in black colored by the axial velocity in four phases of the oscillation period. The arrows indicate movement of the vortices.

jets. As neither of these parameters change appreciably due to the optimization, the effect of these transitory flow features are similar throughout the geometries studied. The RANS model then represents the large-scale impact to the flow pattern driven by changes in combustor geometry.

Pressure loss between the RANS and fine grid LES models also differs. This is due to the enforcement of a symmetry plane in the RANS model. The pressure loss is directly tied to the total area of the jets [15], and given that only half of the jets are modeled with RANS, we expect this value to be much lower. As the differences highlighted between the two models remain similar for all geometries studied, we are confident that the RANS model provides an adequate measure of performance for the purpose of narrowing the parameter space during the optimization phase.

3 Sensitivity Analysis

To reduce the number of parameters included in the optimization described in Section 4, we performed a sensitivity analysis to identify the geometric parameters that have the most significant impact on the mixing quality and turbulence intensity of the combustor. We examined the contribution of each individual parameter to these objectives, in addition to contributions from parameter combinations. We considered the aspect ratio, diameter, and spacing between the jets, as well as the height of the jet chutes for each row individually. We also investigated the axial distance and transverse offset between the two rows of jets.

These parameters have all been identified in prior work as having potentially significant impacts on combustor performance. Salewski *et al.* [27] showed that the jet aspect ratio, defined as the ratio of axial (x) and transverse (z) jet diameters, plays an important role in the formation of large coherent structures, enhancing mixing behavior. Similarly, the spacing between adjacent jets can impact mixing quality due to the interaction of the counter-rotating vortex pair (CVP) emanating from the jet, which is responsible for entrainment of the crossflow. Numerous studies have shown the momentum-to-flux ratio of the jets to be the most important factor in predicting the downstream combustor flow field [28–30]. Because the number of jets and inlet velocity are fixed in the present study, the jet diameter is the parameter responsible for adjusting the momentum-to-flux ratio. A primary mode by which the momentum-to-flux ratio impacts mixing is through jet penetration, which may also be altered through the addition of chutes to the jets [1,15]. It is known from Lefebvre [15] that the pressure loss, and similarly jet penetration when inlet velocity is held constant, can be attributed directly to the effective area of the jets, thus the aspect ratio and diameter. However, there is not a

Table 3 Combustor parameter ranges, showing lower and upper bounds, selected for exploration in the sensitivity analysis

Parameter	Lower	Upper
Aspect ratio	0.6	2.2
Jet minor radius (mm)	10	40
Jet spacing (mm)	20	60
Chuted jet height (mm)	5	40
Spacing between rows (mm)	40	100
Transverse offset between rows (mm)	0	40

linear relationship between the parameters and mixing uniformity, and it is the nature of this relationship that was investigated in the sensitivity analysis.

In addition to these parameters, we also hypothesize that the spacing between the two rows of jets will impact turbulence intensity at the exit, as a longer length will allow more dissipation of turbulent eddies. The transverse offset between the first and second row was also considered. Mechanisms of interaction between the CVPs in an offset versus aligned design may further impact turbulence intensity and mixing.

In the following, we outline the specific methodology used to perform the sensitivity analysis, which included both RANS simulations and surrogate modeling, and then provide the results from the analysis. Ultimately, out of 10 total parameters considered, we identify 7 that are the most significant – these are the parameters included in the optimization described in Section 4.

3.1 Methodology. To begin the sensitivity study, we first performed Latin hypercube sampling (LHS) with the Dakota software developed at Sandia National Laboratories [31]. A total of 500 different designs (or samples, $N_s = 500$) were evaluated with the RANS model described in Section 2.4. Each parameter was varied within the ranges shown in Table 3, which were chosen based on reasonable design constraints to not add substantial additional weight to the combustor. To perform the LHS sampling, each of the $n = 10$ parameter ranges was divided into $N_s = 500$ segments of equal probability, where N_s is the number of samples and n is the number of parameters. The length of each segment was normally distributed across the range of each parameter, with mean values holding the largest segment. Values within each segment were selected at random using the Mersenne Twister random number generator [32]. The selected parameter values were then shuffled at random and combined to create a set of N_s vectors of n -length. Correlations between the n -dimensions were reduced by means of a Choleski decomposition [11]. This ensured that samples were evenly distributed, with each column and row of the $N_s \times n$ hypercube having exactly one sample.

For the sensitivity study, we formulated an objective function based on the turbulence intensity at the exit of the combustor, I_{RANS} defined in Eq. (10), and the deviation of the mixing uniformity, M_{RANS} defined in Eq. (11), from the baseline design. Both turbulence intensity and mixing performance were spatially averaged over the combustor exit plane. A linear combination of the two parameters was used as the basis for the objective function. In order to determine relative weightings, the $N_s = 500$ designs evaluated with the RANS model were analyzed. The following combination was found to adequately prioritize the minimization of the turbulence intensity while still retaining mixing performance:

$$O_S = |M_{\text{RANS}} - 0.883| + 2I_{\text{RANS}}. \quad (12)$$

The subtraction of 0.883 from M_{RANS} is added to account for the mixing uniformity of the baseline design.

A surrogate model was created using an artificial neural network trained directly on the results from the 500 designs evaluated with the RANS model. The network was a stochastic layered perceptron model developed by Zimmerman [33] that leverages a closed-form

Table 4 Surrogate quality metrics at training data points and with 10-fold cross-validation.

	Mean Objective Value	R^2	Mean Absolute Error	Maximum Absolute Error	Root-Mean Squared Error
At model training points	0.7215	0.90	7.2%	48.2%	9.4%
10-fold cross-validation	0.7247	-	10.1%	72.0%	13.4%

solution to the training problem using simple matrix operations, yielding an inexpensive approach. The activation function used in this instance was a hyperbolic tangent of the form

$$f_A(\mathbf{x}) \approx \tanh \{ \tanh [(\mathbf{x}\mathbf{A}_0 + \boldsymbol{\theta}_0)\mathbf{A}_1 + \boldsymbol{\theta}_1] \}, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{x} is a point in n -dimensional parameter space and \mathbf{A}_i and $\boldsymbol{\theta}_i$ are the matrices and vectors corresponding to the middle layer weighting values and threshold bias values, respectively. These values were optimized during the training period using a singular value decomposition method and can be compared to those polynomial coefficients generated in a quadratic surface fit.

The method for sensitivity analysis was the evaluation of the total Sobol index for each parameter [34]. The total Sobol index represents the percentage of variation in the objective function that a given parameter is responsible for, including interactions with other parameters. All parameters with a sensitivity above 5% were selected for optimization. This method was chosen as the model is non-linear and non-additive, and we were interested in the interaction between parameters. The variance of a parameter is calculated by holding the parameter at a fixed value and integrating over the remaining parameters. Monte Carlo sampling approximations were used to estimate the integrals, rather than considering all possible combinations of inputs. The main source of error in this approach is a limited number of samples. Considering this, we used the surrogate model to generate $N_{\text{SOBOL}} = 2000$ samples. Initially, two independent populations of size N_{SOBOL} were generated where all $n = 10$ parameters were varied, denoted by the matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} . Next, n additional populations of size N_{SOBOL} were created by taking one column from \mathbf{X} and swapping this with the same column in \mathbf{Y} , giving \mathbf{Y}_X . The total Sobol indices are then given by

$$S_{Ti} = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{N_{\text{SOBOL}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{SOBOL}}} f_A([\mathbf{Y}]_j) f_A([\mathbf{Y}_X^{(i)}]_j) - \langle f_A(\mathbf{Y}) \rangle^2}{\frac{1}{N_{\text{SOBOL}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{SOBOL}}} f_A([\mathbf{Y}]_j)^2 - \langle f_A(\mathbf{Y}) \rangle^2}, \quad (14)$$

where $[\cdot]_j$ denotes the j^{th} row of the enclosed matrix, $\mathbf{Y}_X^{(i)}$ is the matrix where the i^{th} column of \mathbf{Y} has been replaced with the corresponding column from \mathbf{X} , and $\langle \cdot \rangle$ is mean value of all N_{SOBOL} -function evaluations defined by

$$\langle f_A(\mathbf{Y}) \rangle = \frac{1}{N_{\text{SOBOL}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{SOBOL}}} f_A([\mathbf{Y}]_j). \quad (15)$$

This results in a total of $N_{\text{SOBOL}}(n + 2)$ function evaluations, totaling 24,000 function evaluations with the surrogate model.

3.2 Results. Given the importance of the surrogate model in performing the sensitivity analysis, we first began by assessing its quality. Model quality at the training data points and using a 10-fold cross-validation is shown in Table 4. During 10-fold cross validation, the training data is divided into 10 groups at random. One group is left out as the test points, while the other remaining 9 groups are used as the surrogate model training data. This provides a test metric for the functional quality of the model. The R^2 of this model is 0.9, which is reasonable accuracy when considering the complexities of turbulence and turbulence modeling. While the maximum absolute errors for both the training data and cross-validation data are high, it should be noted that this was only

Table 5 Sensitivities acquired from total Sobol indices for primary zone and dilution jet geometric parameters.

	Parameter	Sensitivity
Primary Zone	Aspect ratio	25.6%
	Diameter	25.5%
	Spacing	7.1%
	Chute height	11.5%
Dilution	Aspect ratio	16.6%
	Diameter	25.6%
	Spacing	5.0%
	Chute height	2.7%
Rows	Axial spacing	2.2%
	Transverse offset	3.1%

observed in less than 5 cases (1% of the population). The mean absolute errors and root mean squared errors are acceptably low for the purposes of this study.

The results of the sensitivity analysis showed that the aspect ratio, diameter and spacing of both the primary zone and dilution jets are important, as well as the chute height of the primary jets (Table 5). The aspect ratio and the diameter were shown to have the greatest impact with sensitivities on the order of 25%. This is strongly in line with what has been shown in literature ([27–30], where the aspect ratio and diameter were shown to significantly alter the formation of coherent structures. The spacing of the jets was also found to be influential. In RANS, the counter-rotating vortex pair is not apparent, however the spacing has been shown to impact the merge and combine points of parallel jets, which in turn alters mixing and turbulence intensity [35]. When the influence of vortex development is also investigated, it is likely that the spacing will have an even greater impact.

Based on the results in Table 5, we include all four parameters describing the primary zone jets, all dilution jet parameters except for the chute height, and none of the row parameters in the optimization described in the next section. Through the sensitivity analysis we have therefore reduced the original set of 10 parameters to only 7 parameters used in the optimization.

4 Multi-Fidelity Optimization

4.1 Methodology. The optimization methodology is based on a machine learning, surrogate-assisted genetic algorithm in a multi-fidelity approach. The unstable, non-linear nature of turbulence leads to a complex objective function space that does not readily permit the use of gradient-based optimization methods. This is exemplified in Fig. 7, which shows the variation in turbulence intensity against the first two principal components from a principle component analysis [36] when the parameters are each varied within ± 0.127 mm. No obvious patterns are evident in the resulting turbulence intensity and the scatter is indicative of the need for a stochastic optimization method.

The complete algorithm for the optimization methodology is shown in Alg. 1. Initially we used the RANS model with surrogate assistance to narrow the parameter space to a locale in which the global optimum is expected to exist. Optimization with the RANS model was then followed by surrogate-assisted optimization using a coarse grid LES. Both the RANS and LES optimization stages leveraged a genetic algorithm consisting of six main components: initialization and evaluation of a parent population, crossover and

mutation to create a child generation, updating of the elite population, and assessment of convergence.

4.1.1 Objective function. The objective function minimized during the optimization was based on the turbulence intensity calculated using Eq. (4) or (10) for the LES or RANS simulations, respectively. We set the maximum mixing non-uniformity defined in Eq. (6) and (11) as a constraint in the optimization, with a penalty added to the objective function for any mixing uniformity worse than the baseline design. Based on the mixing uniformity results for the baseline configuration in Tables 1 and 2, this limit was set to 0.903 for the RANS optimization, providing a slight buffer, and 0.186 for the LES optimization.

Upper and lower limits for the pressure drop across the combustor were also added as constraints. The pressure loss was calculated as the percentage decrease in total pressure from the inlet to the exit of the combustor. In gas turbine combustor design, the high velocity crossflow driven by the pressure drop across the combustor is used to further atomize the fuel and create high turbulent mixing for sustained combustion in the primary zone. However, a low pressure drop is also desired to minimize the loss of pressure rise achieved in the compressor. The constraint was set to $1.6 \leq \Delta p \leq 2.63\%$ for the RANS optimization and $2.5 \leq \Delta p \leq 4.05\%$ for the LES optimization in accordance with the performance of the baseline design outlined in Tables 1 and 2 and allowing for a slight buffer due to the observation of pressure loss in the coarse grid LES noted in Section 2.3.

A lower limit on the jet penetration of the primary zone jets was additionally included as a constraint in the RANS optimization to ensure that an adequate recirculation zone developed. This was achieved at a minimum penetration of 0.134 m and was evaluated in the optimization by examining the degradation of jet velocity in the y-direction. A limit on jet penetration was not added for the LES optimization, as it was determined that all designs within the LES optimization bounds had a strong recirculation zone. In all instances, the penalty applied to the objective function was the difference between the evaluated design and the closest bound.

4.1.2 Surrogate assisted genetic algorithm. Within the genetic algorithm, the set of parameters for a given design were transformed into a binary representation. The “fitness” described throughout this work is the evaluation of the objective function with penalties included. The population was initialized with LHS to ensure a uniform distribution across the parameter space. We determined population size according to the methods developed

by Goldberg *et al.* [37]. The size of the population, taking into account noise effects, is given as

$$P_s = c(l - m)2^{m-1}, \quad (16)$$

where m is the highest order of the contributing schema, as discussed in Goldberg *et al.* [37], c is chosen for the desired level of statistical significance to minimize the difference between the fitness average of the best and second best schema, and l is the length of the binary string for all parameters concatenated. Only first-order schema were found to contribute to the fitness average. A significance level of 0.078 was chosen, giving a value of c equal to 2.12. The binary string length for each parameter was chosen to be 12, as this provided ample precision. From this, we selected the population size to be 176.

We evaluated the initial parent population using the RANS model. The individuals evaluated with the RANS model then formed the basis of the training database for the same surrogate model methodology developed in the sensitivity analysis described in Section 3. We assessed the top 20 regions of the surrogate model with the highest discrepancy between predicted and actual turbulence intensities. We conducted additional LHS sampling in these regions, for a total of 100 additional samples evaluated with the RANS model and added to the training database.

Because the initial quality of the surrogate model in predicting the jet penetration was inadequate, a similar adaptive sampling scheme was used in regions of the highest discrepancy between the predicted and actual jet penetration for a total of 50 additional samples. By using this pseudo-adaptive sampling approach, we vastly improved the quality of the surrogate model.

A tournament selection was used to determine parent individuals for the next generation. Individuals were selected at random from the population and the individual with the highest fitness was chosen to proceed. The number of individuals entered into the tournament was designated to be 2.8% of the population. Widening the tournament size increases the selection pressure, as there is a larger chance that the best performing individuals are passed on. The degree of selection pressure in the algorithm was considered to prevent early convergence to an incorrect solution, which may happen if the pressure is too high [38]. When selecting the parent population, the number of individuals assigned remained the same as the population size.

We performed uniform crossover on the parent population to produce an equal number of offspring. Each individual was first converted to a binary representation. Bit-wise crossing then occurred at random between two parents. The independent probability of each bit being exchanged was set at 0.9 based on findings from Gibbs *et al.* [39].

Mutation was performed on individual bits to mimic natural errors in replication when creating the offspring. Mutation is necessary for evolution of the population and to prevent the algorithm from becoming stalled in local minima [40]. Schaffer *et al.* [40] have shown that there is a positive relationship between the most suitable mutation probability and the population size. Based on this study, the mutation rate was selected to be a function of the population size, $p_m = 5/P_s$, and dictated the independent probability of each bit being flipped.

We evaluated the children with the surrogate model. To improve the performance of the surrogate model as further solutions were explored, the top 20 children were evaluated directly with the RANS model. These individuals and their corresponding fitnesses were then added to the surrogate model training database. The omission of the top 20 children from the surrogate model training database was also trialed. The optimization converged, but to a less favorable outcome. Therefore, we proceeded with the continuous-learning approach.

The genetic algorithm efficiency was improved by retaining an elitist population of size N_E . The top ten members from each population, $N_E = 10$, were included in the subsequent population to ensure that the best solutions were not lost in the evolutionary

Fig. 7 Turbulence intensity using principal component analysis for 100 sample points varying each parameter by ± 0.127 mm.

Algorithm 1 : Optimization Scheme

Build Surrogate Model

Initialize population with LHS sampling

Evaluate fitness of initial population with RANS model

Build initial surrogate model training database from population

Identify top 20 regions of surrogate model with highest turbulence intensity deviation from RANS model

for $i=1:20$ **do**

Perform 5 LHS samples in region

Add to surrogate training database

end for

Identify top 10 regions of surrogate model with highest jet penetration deviation from RANS model

for $i=1:10$ **do**

Perform 5 LHS samples in region

Add to surrogate training database

end for**Perform Optimization with RANS Model****while** $T > 0.4\%(T_{\text{initial}} - 25)$ **do**

Select parent individuals

Perform crossover

Perform mutation

Evaluate fitness of children with surrogate model

 Apply penalties to objective function for $\Delta p > 2.63\%$ or $\Delta p < 1.6\%$, mixing non-uniformities > 0.903 , and inadequate jet penetration

Sort child population from best to worst fitness

for $j=1:20$ **do**

Evaluate individual[j] with RANS model

Add individual [j] to surrogate model training database

end for Update elite population of $N_E = 10$ Calculate T (convergence metric)**end while****Perform Optimization with Coarse Grid LES Model**

Determine parameter bounds for LES optimization from top 20 individuals

Initialize surrogate model training database with 100 LHS samples

Initialize population with LHS sampling

Evaluate fitness of initial population with surrogate model

while $T > 25$ **do**

Select parent individuals

Perform crossover

Perform mutation

Evaluate fitness of children with surrogate model

 Apply penalties to objective function for $\Delta p > 4.05\%$ or $\Delta p < 2.5\%$ and mixing non-uniformities > 0.186

Sort child population from best to worst fitness

for $j=1:10$ **do**

Evaluate individual[j] with LES model

Add individual [j] to surrogate model training database

end for Update elite population of $N_E = 20$ Calculate T **end while**

operations. As better solutions were found, this population was updated. The composition of the subsequent generation was then the elitist population and the top $P_s - N_E$ children.

To determine the stopping criteria for the genetic algorithm, we adopted the idea of temperature [41]. A “temperature” for the algorithm was calculated by quantifying the difference in fitness of the elite population from generation to generation against a baseline, which in this work was selected to be 25° . A “hot” algorithm is one in which the average elite population fitness has substantial changes between generations, resulting in higher temperatures. Cooling of the algorithm to the baseline temperature is used to identify convergence to an optimal solution. Our methodology formulated the temperature as

$$T_{\text{new}} = T_0 e^{10|O_{TI,\text{new}} - O_{TI,\text{old}}|}, \quad (17)$$

where $T_0 = 25$, $O_{TI,\text{new}}$ is the average fitness of the elite members in the new generation, and $O_{TI,\text{old}}$ is the average fitness of the elite members in the previous generation. The average fitness of the elite members was used instead of the fitness of the best member to prevent premature convergence. The algorithm was stopped when the temperature reached 0.4% of the difference between the initial temperature and 25° (99.6% converged). Typically, a tighter convergence would be desired, but the purpose of the optimization in this context was only to select a refined region in which optimization with the LES model should be performed, given the increased computational load of this model.

We then repeated this optimization with slight variations to the number of children directly evaluated and in the elite population, this time using the coarse grid LES model described in Section 2.2. We used the maximum and minimum bounds of each parameter taken from the top 20 individuals at the completion of the RANS optimization as the parameter bounds for the LES optimization. This created a significantly reduced parameter space that made optimization with a relatively expensive model feasible.

Rather than using the initial parent population as the basis for the surrogate model, we instead used the results from 100 LHS samples. This was done to minimize computational burden. The population size remained the same as previously, being initialized with LHS sampling and evaluated using the surrogate model. The top 10 performing individuals were then evaluated with the LES model and these results added to the surrogate model training database. The crossover and mutation properties of the optimization were kept the same as in the RANS optimization. As computational resources were limited, we opted to increase the tournament size from 2.8% to 5.7% of the population to promote quicker convergence.

While the initial quality of the surrogate model for turbulence intensity and pressure loss remained acceptable, the initial quality of the model for mixing uniformity was unsatisfactory. Rather than taking a pseudo-adaptive sampling approach as done with the RANS optimization, we instead elected to increase the size of the elite population to $N_E = 20$ to account for the additional uncertainty. We determined the final optimized solution to be the leading solution after the temperature remained at 25° (no change to the elite population) for a minimum of two generations.

Table 6 Ranges of primary zone and dilution jet geometric parameters during the RANS optimization.

	Parameter	Lower	Upper
Primary zone	Aspect ratio	0.6	3.2
	Minor radius (mm)	10	25
	Spacing (mm)	20	100
	Chute height (mm)	5	40
Dilution	Aspect ratio	0.6	3.5
	Minor radius (mm)	10	25
	Spacing (mm)	20	100

4.2 Results. The parameter space explored at the start of the RANS optimization was appreciably large in order to identify the region in which the global minimum exists. The limits used for each of the 7 parameters included in the optimization are shown in Table 6. The lower bound of the jet aspect ratio was set based on geometric constraints. It was observed throughout sampling conducted with the RANS simulations that any design with a primary jet aspect ratio higher than 3.2 did not provide adequate jet penetration and the development of a recirculation zone. Therefore, this was set as the upper limit for the primary jets. Adequate jet penetration was not a concern for the dilution jets, as these jets do not contribute to the development of a recirculation zone. The upper limit for the dilution jets was instead determined by geometric constraints. The remainder of the parameter limits were set based on what was deemed reasonable from a design perspective so as to not add appreciable weight to the combustor.

As with the sensitivity analysis in Section 3, we assessed the quality and accuracy of the surrogate model used in the RANS optimization. A separate surrogate model was used for each objective and constraint, resulting in four surrogate models. The improvement in quality of the surrogate models with subsequent sampling is shown in Table 7. A drastic increase in quality is observed across all surrogate models after sampling on areas which showed the highest discrepancy in turbulence intensity, with R^2 values increasing from 0.617 and 0.779 to 0.877 and 0.995. Further sampling in regions which showed the largest discrepancies in jet penetration improved the R^2 of the jet penetration surrogate model appreciably, however there was little effect on the remaining surrogate models. The R^2 of the mixing uniformity and jet penetration models decrease after the completion of optimization, where the top individuals have been added to the training database for each generation. This is believed to be due to a high concentration of training data points in one specific region of the parameter space, where local fluctuations in the objective function are high (Fig. 2). A perfect R^2 was noted for the pressure loss surrogate model. It is believed that this is due to the fact that pressure loss can alternatively be calculated directly from the total jet area and mass flow [15], thus there is a known direct correlation.

The genetic algorithm used in the RANS optimization was run to 99.6% convergence as determined by the temperature expression of Eq. (17). Convergence to this level was achieved with 12 generations and 566 total RANS evaluations. The leading solution at the end of the RANS optimization attained a turbulence intensity of 15.1%, which was a 1.5% improvement from the initial generation. This solution exhibited a pressure loss of 2.579% and a mixing uniformity of 0.698.

We utilized the parameter limits from the top 20 individuals as the bounds for the LES optimization, as shown in Table 8. The region of the parameter space identified by the RANS optimization showed narrowed jets, with larger jets in the primary row. The

Table 7 RANS surrogate model metrics initially, after refining on largest turbulence intensity (TI) deviations, after refining on the largest jet penetration (JP) deviations, and after final optimization. The top row for each level of refinement shows the R^2 value and the second row shows the RMSE divided by the mean value for TI, mixing uniformity, pressure loss (Δp), and the JP.

	TI	Mixing	Δp	JP
Initial	0.707	0.779	1.000	0.617
	11.55%	16.49%	4.52%	57.72%
TI refinement	0.970	0.948	0.995	0.877
	4.44%	10.01%	3.67%	28.64%
JP refinement	0.970	0.949	1.000	0.904
	5.03%	8.99%	3.60%	27.72%
Final	0.980	0.907	1.000	0.901
	3.83%	7.79%	3.93%	25.75%

Table 8 Ranges of primary zone and dilution jet geometric parameters during the LES optimization.

	Parameter	Lower	Upper
Primary zone	Aspect ratio	2.214	3.185
	Minor radius (mm)	19.3	22.7
	Spacing (mm)	45.5	92.3
	Chute height (mm)	7.8	39.5
Dilution	Aspect ratio	2.728	3.481
	Minor radius (mm)	13.8	17.8
	Spacing (mm)	30.9	86.6

Table 9 LES surrogate model metrics initially and after optimization (details on the rows and columns are provided in the caption of Table 7).

	TI	Mixing	Δp
Initial	0.916	0.511	1.000
	11.55%	16.49%	4.52%
Final	0.887	0.305	0.997
	3.58%	23.95%	4.32%

bounds for jet spacing and jet chute height remained quite broad, suggesting that the parameters with the largest impact on turbulence intensity were the aspect ratio and jet diameter. This is consistent with results from the sensitivity study in Section 3.

As noted in Section 4.1, because all designs within the bounds in Table 8 demonstrated strong recirculation zones, the constraint for a minimum jet penetration was eliminated from consideration during the LES optimization. The pressure drop across the combustor can be directly attributed to the effective area of the jets [15]. The limit for pressure loss was increased to $\Delta p > 4.05\%$ or $\Delta p < 2.5\%$ as the symmetry plane in the computational domain was removed in the coarse-grid LES, increasing the pressure drop due to increased total jet area. Similarly, the maximum mixing non-uniformity was decreased to 0.186 to account for the additional mixing that occurs as a result of the additional flow features noted in Section 2.5.

The initial quality of the LES turbulence intensity and pressure loss surrogate models were acceptable, but the mixing uniformity surrogate model exhibited poor performance with an R^2 of 0.511 (Table 9). Given the computational expense of additional model evaluations, we chose to increase the number of individuals in the elite population to account for uncertainty in this metric. The LES optimization was run to full convergence, defined by no change to the elite population for a minimum of two generations. This was achieved in 11 generations with a total of 210 LES model evaluations.

The leading solution at the end of the LES optimization had a turbulence intensity of 13.9%, which was a 2% improvement from the initial generation. The pressure loss and mixing uniformity

Fig. 8 Comparison of baseline (a) and optimized (b) combustor jet geometries

Table 10 Comparison of primary zone and dilution jet geometric parameters for the baseline and optimized designs.

	Parameter	Baseline	Optimized
Primary zone	Aspect ratio	2.027	3.176
	Minor radius (mm)	18.75	21.70
	Spacing (mm)	40.00	57.59
	Chute height (mm)	40.00	25.02
Dilution	Aspect ratio	2.027	3.219
	Minor radius (mm)	18.75	14.51
	Spacing (mm)	40.00	70.11

Table 11 Results for key flow parameters at $x = 0.525$ m downstream from the combustor exit.

Parameter at Combustor Exit	Baseline	Optimized
Average turbulence intensity	17.55%	12.20%
Mixing uniformity metric	0.186	0.236
Pressure loss	3.97%	3.55%
Maximum normalized velocity	1.10	1.06
Integral time scale	1.5 ms	1.2 ms
Integral length scale	50.9 mm	46.5 mm
Mean flow angle	4.72°	0.93°
Max flow angle	13.81°	5.15°

achieved were 3.95% and 0.188, respectively. This leading solution is referred to as the optimized design from this point forward. A comparison of the baseline and optimized jet geometries is shown in Fig. 8, with corresponding geometric parameters provided in Table 10. The optimized solution favors narrow jets for both the primary zone and dilution jets with similar aspect ratios. The size of the primary jets is substantially larger than the dilution jets. The spacing between jets for both rows is increased from the baseline design. We also see an appreciable decrease in the primary jet chute height.

To confirm the quality of the optimized design, we performed a fine grid LES for the new geometry. The optimized combustor length exceeds that of the baseline design by 0.16 m, with both designs maintaining an equivalent distance between the primary and dilution jet rows. The elongation of the jets in the optimized design is the cause of this extended length. When assessments are carried out at a location 0.525 m downstream of the combustor exit, mirroring the baseline design measurements, we observe a further reduction in turbulence intensity. A comparison of key flow properties between the baseline and optimized designs is shown in Table 11. The decrease in turbulence intensity is significant, demonstrating a 5.35% improvement. We also observe a reduction in the pressure loss of 0.42%. The integral time scale is slightly smaller in the optimized design, suggesting a quicker decay of turbulence. We see that the integral length scale has also shortened, suggesting a decrease in the characteristic size of turbulent eddies. The flow angles indicate a notably more uniform flow profile, corresponding to the reduction in turbulence intensity.

The temporally averaged turbulence intensity and mixing uniformity fields at the measurement plane are shown in Fig. 9. The standard deviation of the turbulence intensity is unchanged from the baseline design with some upstream flow features retained. Vast improvements in the overall turbulence intensity are noted. The mixing non-uniformity is more than that of the baseline design by 14%. We chose the limit during LES optimization to be that of the fine grid baseline LES (0.186), not the coarse grid LES (0.154), as it was not known what the relationship was between the two models. As can be seen by comparing the mixing uniformity of the optimized solution from the fine grid LES and coarse grid LES, it does appear that the mixing uniformity scales proportionally between the two. This accounts for the increased non-uniformity in the optimized design, as the limit was in retrospect set too high. The optimization method presented in this work successfully adheres to all constraints provided and shows a substantial decrease

in exit turbulence intensity. The intent of this work is to demonstrate a novel optimization method for highly complex and chaotic problems, which we have successfully demonstrated.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we demonstrated a machine learning, multi-fidelity stochastic optimization method for tailoring the exit turbulence field of a gas turbine combustor. We showed that by modifying the primary and dilution jet geometric parameters we can decrease the turbulence intensity at the combustor exit while maintaining mixing performance and minimal pressure loss.

The optimization method used a genetic algorithm and had three layers of fidelity with increasing complexity: a continuously-learning surrogate model built via an artificial neural network, a RANS model used to narrow the parameter space, and a coarse grid LES model to perform the final optimization. We began with the development of a fine grid LES to validate against prior experimental results. Two simplified models were then derived from this LES, one being the same LES performed on a coarsened grid and the other a RANS model that halved the computational domain through introducing a symmetry plane. A metric for mixing performance of the combustor was developed based on the uniformity of an injected passive scalar at the combustor exit. A sensitivity study was then performed to determine which aspects of the combustor geometry contributed most to the turbulence field and mixing uniformity at the exit, which we achieved via evaluation of total Sobol indices. From this, we identified 7 parameters that most affected the outcome: the aspect ratio, diameter, and spacing of both the primary and dilution jets, and the chute height of the primary jets.

We used the turbulence intensity at the combustor exit as the objective function to minimize. Penalties were added for unfavorable mixing uniformity, increased pressure loss, and inadequate jet penetration. The training database for the surrogate model was built from the RANS evaluations of the initial parent population, which was generated through LHS. Tournament selection was conducted to determine the parent population for the next generation. Crossover and mutation operations were then performed to generate the children. An elite population was retained to further enhance the performance of the algorithm. Of the children population, the top 20 individuals identified by the surrogate model were evaluated with the RANS model. The results from these simulations were then added to the surrogate model training database. We developed an exponential convergence metric based on the idea of a “hot” or “cold” algorithm. Optimization with the RANS model

Fig. 9 Comparison of turbulence intensity and mixing uniformity fields for the baseline design (top) and the optimized design (bottom).

was run to 99.6% convergence before switching to optimization with the coarse grid LES. The surrogate model was rebuilt for optimization with the LES from 100 LHS. The parameter space was significantly narrowed by setting parameter limits to those obtained from the top 20 individuals identified by the RANS optimization. The settings of the genetic algorithm remained the same for both optimization campaigns, with the exception of the elite population size which was increased from 10 to 20 for the LES optimization. The RANS optimization converged within 12 generations and the LES optimization within 11 generations.

The leading solution at the completion of the LES optimization was evaluated with the fine grid LES and compared to the baseline design. We achieved a 5.35% decrease in turbulence intensity at the exit, a 0.42% decrease in pressure loss across the combustor, and a 14% increase in mixing non-uniformity. The latter resulted from the constraint limits set in the LES optimization phase and can be improved with updated limits. We demonstrated the ability of this method to optimize the exit flow field of the combustor while meeting all constraints. Its use shows its promise in handling problems with a high degree of non-linearity and complexity.

The potential applications of this method extend beyond the present work to any problem of high computational expense in which gradient-based optimization is unsuccessful. Future work will include investigation into the mechanisms responsible for decreased turbulence intensity so that these practices can be applied in combustor design. We plan to expand the utilization of this optimization method in the context of a reacting combustor, which will be engine representative and have the additional ability to constrain for NO_x production and temperature pattern.

Acknowledgments

J.A.M. and P.E.H. acknowledge support from NSF award 1847111, as well as the use of HPC computing resources provided by the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) on the Frontera supercomputer.

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